

READING DIFFICULTIES OF GRADE 1 LEARNERS AND THE CHALLENGES FACED BY TEACHERS IN TEACHING READING: A CASE OF LEGISLATIVE DISTRICT 3, ISABELA

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ABSTRACT

Grade 1 learners often struggle with developing foundational reading skills crucial for their academic success and overall literacy development. However, limited research has been conducted on the specific challenges faced by teachers in addressing these reading difficulties within the context of public elementary schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela, highlighting a need to explore this issue comprehensively. This study examines the reading difficulties of Grade 1 learners and the challenges faced by teachers in teaching reading in public elementary schools within Legislative District 3, Isabela, during the 2023-2024 school year. Employing a descriptive survey research design, the study integrates both quantitative and qualitative approaches to analyze the current conditions and relationships between variables. Data were collected using structured questionnaires, unstructured interviews, and documentary analysis. Findings revealed that Grade 1 learners frequently exhibit reading difficulties caused by various factors, while teachers effectively employ diverse strategies and measures to address these issues. However, teachers also face serious challenges in reading instruction, emphasizing the need for sustained support and capacity-building initiatives. The study concludes that no significant differences exist between the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding the identified reading difficulties and challenges. Recommendations include continued use of effective methods, addressing instructional challenges, and expanding research scope to include broader contexts.

Keywords: *Reading Difficulties, Grade 1 Learners, Teaching Challenges, Descriptive Survey, Public Elementary Schools*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a component of literacy that would develop if children were actively guided and involved in their development. It is more complex because children need to be aware of the phonetic structure of spoken language and then decode the alphabetic code to acquire the letter-phone connections. It is the most important goal of the early school years (EGRA Ethiopia, 2014).

The National Institute for Literacy (2007) defines reading as a complex system of deriving meaning from print that requires the ability and knowledge to understand how phonemes or sounds of speech relate to print, the ability to decipher unfamiliar words, the ability to read fluently, sufficient background information and vocabulary to promote reading comprehension, and the ability to construct meaning from prints and the development of maintaining reading motivation. Children must use this skill in early grades (1-4) to understand the meaning of written and printed material and Facilitate language acquisition, communication, and the exchange of ideas and information (Reutzel & Cooter, 2010). Reading difficulties can create challenges in school and result in learners being stigmatized in the classroom.

Reading skills are usually taught during the first three years of primary education so that as children progress in their education, they can understand the concepts they are taught (Paananen, 2009). In addition, research has shown that there are high chances for children who have not acquired reading skills by grade 3 or 4 to develop reading problems, In other words, the ability to read becomes useful if one is to gain more knowledge. This is so because; the growing technicalization of society has brought increasing demands for literacy.

However, most learners are unable to use reading as a tool for learning new information. Reading difficulties are usually detected in childhood, but it takes someone knowledgeable to Identify that a child has a reading difficulty. If no interventions are put in place, reading difficulties can affect someone through adulthood (Matafwali, 2009).

There seems to be great controversy on what the causes of reading difficulties are. Some scholars relate reading difficulties to neurological factors while others relate them to environmental factors. Discussions have been held in the United States of America and Scandinavian countries to find out whether reading difficulties are caused by psychological or neurological factors. Reading difficulties are complex, and the causes are difficult to pinpoint (Maruyama, 2012).

The ability to read is an essential skill for learners to master because information is presented in text throughout the world. Educational systems rely more heavily upon text as students reach higher grade levels. In early elementary grades, learners do not typically have textbooks at home and they primarily work with decodable readers and short stories borrowed from the library (Cimmiyotti, 2013).

However, beginning around third grade, textbooks are introduced to the home environment, and learner's abilities to pull and process information from textbooks become increasingly necessary for student achievement. By the time learners reach high school, many history teachers expect learners to build their background knowledge by reading at home and then demonstrate their understanding during in-class discussions. The textbooks that students utilize in science, math, and history are typically several hundred pages in length, featuring diagrams, pictures, and primarily, text to transmit knowledge about the subject to the reader. English teachers also assign novels and stories for reading at home.

Unfortunately, textbooks are challenging for learners to access. Textbooks use advanced vocabulary, cover a vast number of topics, use direct language that doesn't engage the reader, and lack the structure that promotes reading comprehension. In primary school, learners are still building their reading competence, but at the secondary level, they are expected to have the necessary skills (Bryce, 2011).

Reading means many things to many people. It also plays a vital role in one's success in school. It is one of the most important skills in English an individual must need to master. It is a prerequisite of all learning areas. It serves as a gateway for every student to learn different subjects because when a student has difficulty reading, he may encounter also difficulties in all subject areas (Sanopao, 2016).

Villegas (2015) cited that reading is a source of difficulty for second-language learners. The problems that they encounter are due to several factors including a lack of appropriate reading strategies, lack of background knowledge related to the topic of the target language, or lack of attitudes toward reading, to name a few. Nevertheless, given enough time, learners can overcome their difficulties when they receive the appropriate training.

Pupils need to practice reading to develop their phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension. The mastery of these skills will grant them access to increasingly complex knowledge in other academic subject areas.

It is within this premises that the proponent of this study has been prompted to assess the reading difficulties of Grade 1 learners and the challenges faced by teachers in teaching reading in public elementary schools in legislative District 3, Isabela for the school year 2023-2024. Hence, this study was undertaken.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

The complications of reading and learning how to read can be lost on those who know how to do it. For many people, it's difficult to remember a time when they couldn't read, as many learn while very young learners, or those who learn how to read later in life, the difficulties of reading are clear. To approach these difficulties, literacy experts theorize how reading happens and develop instructional models to help individuals master this complicated process (Hamilton, 2017).

(1) Traditional. Traditional theories of reading suggest it is a process by which individuals learn smaller, discrete words and parts of words before learning how to read whole sentences, paragraphs, and so on. Traditional theories of reading maintain that individuals build up their vocabularies and grammatical rules, and through this act of accretion, they slowly gather together the necessary components to read fluently. These bottom-up theories of reading lend themselves to models of instruction such as phonics-based learning, in which individuals sound out phonemes or parts of words and slowly combine them into whole words, whole words into sentences, and so on.

(2) Cognitive. So-called cognitive theories of reading counteract traditional theories by maintaining that the concept and process of reading are learned first and then broken down into individual words, parts of words, sentences, paragraphs, and so on. These top-down theories of reading believe there's a moment at which individuals understand the process of reading without being entirely familiar with all the discrete components of how to read, such as individual words, how words fit together, etc. Cognitive theories of reading lend themselves to models of instruction like the holistic model that has individuals approach texts as a whole, even if they are not familiar with all the words or phrases or even how the words fit together into sentences. Through context clues and assistance, the holistic model suggests students can eventually decode whole texts, which in turn allows them to decode that text's components (Hamilton, 2017).

(3) Hybrid. As the same suggests, hybrid theories of reading borrow liberally from both traditional and cognitive theories. In hybrid theories, reading is both a top-down and bottom-up approach in that as individuals approach whole texts and decode discrete components of those texts they also build up their vocabularies and personal understanding of grammatical rules which, in turn, helps them decode future whole texts -- which in turn builds their vocabularies and grammars. Hybrid models of reading, much as with hybrid theories of reading, encourage individuals to both compile lists or banks of phonemes, words, sentences, and so on, as well as approach newer and more complicated whole texts as the individual learns how to read

(4) Metacognitive. Metacognitive theories of reading relate to how an individual thinks about his reading processes both before, after, and during the actual act. Metacognitive theories of reading maintain that individuals, regardless of whether they approach reading from traditional, cognitive, or hybrid theories or models of reading. Metacognitive theories of reading lend themselves to modeling practices such as written or spoken reflection following a reading exercise, as well as note-taking on the margins of a page or highlighting lines or passages while reading.

(5) Whole-Language Approach. One of the popular reading theories. This approach suggests that if students are immersed in words, books, and language-rich environments, they will naturally make meanings of words and learn to read. This theory does not utilize specific and direct literacy instruction. Whole language is a

top-down theory of reading. Students are introduced to all of the components of reading at once, and they make meanings while immersed in the literacy process. In this approach, teachers do not establish a basis or foundation for reading instruction (Forstall, 2019).

(6) Bottom 0Up Approach. On the contrary, the theory of reading utilizing the bottom-up reading model involves a step-by-step mastery of reading components so that the student eventually becomes literate.

This theory relies on direct and explicit instruction of the five components of reading throughout early childhood education. The term “bottom-up” is exactly how this process works. The initial focus for early literacy is the instruction of the basic or foundational skills necessary for life-long mastery of literacy and the components of reading. In bottom-up reading activities, students learn to read from the bottom, or foundation, up to concepts like reading comprehension.

The complete process of reading has five main components. For students to become fully literate, the following concepts must be mastered:

- Phonics - Understanding the sounds that correspond with each letter of the alphabet. This includes long and short vowels and other phonetic rules and involves connecting the concept that letters make sounds and sounds make words.
- Phonemic Awareness - Understanding the sounds of letter combinations, such as consonant blends, syllables, and complete words.
- Vocabulary - Understanding what words mean and being able to use them appropriately.
- Fluency - The ability to read with proper speed and expression without errors. Fluent readers read in the way that they speak.
- Reading Comprehension - The ability to recall events, characters, and the main idea of a story or passage after it is read.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

The present study made use of the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model of goal accomplishment. This model has three major components namely: the input, the process, and the output.

The input included the respondent's profile as to age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, present position, latest performance rating, length of teaching service, and level of in-service training attended. It likewise included the respondents' perception of the different methods, strategies, and approaches in reading instruction, the

reading difficulties of pupils, the cause of reading difficulties manifested by pupils, the measures to address reading difficulties, and the challenges faced by teachers in reading instruction.

The process involved the assessments of the learners' reading difficulties and the challenges faced by teachers in teaching reading in public elementary schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela.

The linkage of the input and the process determined the output. Thus, it was expected that the output would bring forth a program that would improve teaching reading among teachers in public elementary schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela.

To conclude the flow of the paradigm, the feedback through a broken line was sent back to the input and the process for suggestions made from the results of the study. This could serve as indices to further improve the reading instruction in public elementary schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela.

Research Questions

The study was undertaken to assess the perceptions of teachers as regards the reading difficulties of Grade 1 learners and challenges faced by teachers in teaching reading in public elementary schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela for the school year 2023-2024.

To achieve the specific objectives set within the main purpose of this study, an attempt was made to find the answers to the following key research questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondent in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Civil status
 - 1.4 Highest educational attainment
 - 1.5 Present position
 - 1.6 Latest performance rating
 - 1.7 Length of teaching experience
 - 1.8 Level of in-service training attended
2. To what extent are the different methods, strategies, and approaches used by teachers in reading instruction?
3. How do teacher-respondents perceive the reading difficulties of pupils?
4. What is the extent of manifestation of the different causes of reading difficulties among Grade 1 pupils in public elementary schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela?

5. How do teachers rate the extend of effect of the different measures used by teachers in addressing the reading difficulties of pupils?
6. What are the challenges faced by teachers in reading instruction and to what degree are they felt?
7. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of school heads and teachers in teaching reading in public elementary schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela?

METHODOLOGY

The Research Design

The study employed the descriptive survey design to examine the reading difficulties of grade 1 learners and the challenges faced by teachers in teaching reading in public elementary schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela for the school year 2023-2024.

Because the research is a systematic inquiry, this study employed the dimensions of both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Scholars affirmed that although the terms quantitative and qualitative are generally well-known in society, these types of research are somewhat difficult to define (Wiersma & Jurs, 2005). According to Krathwohl (Krathwohl, 1993), quantitative research refers to research that describes phenomena in numbers and measures, instead of words; whereas qualitative research is that describes the phenomena in words instead of numbers, or measures. Krathwhol's description shows how the dates are presented.

According to Good and Scates (2001), this method is appropriate for determining the current condition of any, group or organization, programs, and many others. The term normative is used because surveys are frequently made to ascertain the normal and typical conditions and practices. They further claimed that these methods are used to organize, analyze, interpret, and report the present situation or status of a group.

Similarly, Debold & Meyer (1999) stated that the descriptive research method is not confined to routine fact-gathering and that predicting and identifying relationships among between variables is the goal of competent investigators or researchers. As in any investigation/ inquiry, the descriptive survey method will examine problematic situations, define the problems and state the hypothesis, select appropriate subjects and materials establish categories for classifying data that are ambiguous and appropriate for the study, and capable of bringing out significant likeness, differences, and relationships, select construct techniques, make discriminating objectives, observations and describe analyze and interpret their findings in clear and precise terms. Best (1999) claimed that descriptive research describes and interprets what is to be investigated and analyzed.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the public elementary schools in Legislative 3 in the Division of Isabela. The province of Isabela was presented as a lone legislative district until 1972. It was part of the presentation of Region II from 1978 to 1984, and from 1984 to 1986, it elected 3 assemblymen at-large. In 1986, it was redistricted into four legislative districts.

However, on September 27, 2018, President Rodrigo Duterte signed Republic Act No. 11080, increasing the legislative districts from four to six, and the congressional district is one of the six congressional districts of the Philippines in the province of Isabela. It has been represented in the House of Representatives since 1987. The district consists of the west-central municipalities of Alicia, Angadanan, Cabatuan, Ramon, and San Mateo. It is currently represented in the 18th Congress by Ian Paul L. Dy of the Nationalist People's Coalition (NPC).

The map of Legislative District 3, Division of Isabela is presented on the next page.

Particulars	School Heads		Teachers	
	F	%		
Alicia North District	3	12.50	5	12.50
Alicia South District	3	12.50	5	12.50
Angadanan District	3	12.50	5	12.50
Cabatuan East District	3	12.50	5	12.50
Cabatuan West District	3	12.50	5	12.50
Ramon District	3	12.50	5	12.50
San Mateo District	3	12.50	5	12.50
San Mateo South District	3	12.50	5	12.50
Total	24	100.00	40	100.00

Data Gathering Instruments

The researcher utilized a structured questionnaire to gather the needed data. It was supplemented by an unstructured interview to check and verify vague responses given by the respondents as well as documentary analysis. These were done during the retrieval of the questionnaire.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire was prepared after a careful and comprehensive review of the related literature and studies. The items were adopted from previous studies. It comprised the following subheadings:

- Part I -Demographic Profile of Respondents
- Part II -Methods, Strategies, and Approaches in Reading Instruction
- Part III -Reading Difficulties of Pupils
- Part IV -Common Causes of Reading Difficulties
- Part V -Measures to Addressing Pupil's Reading Difficulties
- Part VI -Challenges Faced by Teachers in Reading Instruction

Try-out of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire was given a try-out to selected school heads and teachers. They were requested to complete the questionnaire honestly and to offer suggestions for improvement. The suggestions taken served as the basis for the improvement of the questionnaire. The draft was presented to the research adviser for further suggestion.

The suggestions and comments derived from pre-testing and the research adviser were incorporated in the final draft of the questionnaire, after which reproduction and distribution were done.

Scoring of the Questionnaire

The data retrieved were converted into numerical weight using the 5-Point Likert Scale. The researcher classified them into different quantities to enable her to categorize them accordingly.

To determine the extent of use of the different methods, strategies, and approaches in reading instruction, the extent of manifestation of the causes of reading difficulties of pupils, and the extent of use of the different measures to address the reading difficulties of pupils, the researcher made use of the following scale:

Point	Scale	Qualitative Description
5	4.21-5.00	Very Often (VO)
4	3.41-4.20	Often (O)
3	2.61-3.40	Sometimes (SO)
2	1.81-2.60	Seldom (SE)
1	1.00-1.80	Never (N)

To assess the extent of the effect of the different methods, strategies, and approaches in reading instructions, as well as the extent of the effect of the different measures to address the reading difficulties of pupils, the researcher made use of the following scale:

Point	Scale	Qualitative Description
5	4.21-5.00	Very Effective (VE)
4	3.41-4.20	Effective (E)
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Effective (ME)
2	1.81-2.60	Slightly Effective (SE)
1	1.00-1.80	Least Effective (LE)

To gauge the extent of the challenges faced by teachers in reading instruction, the researcher used the following scale.

Point	Scale	Qualitative Description
5	4.21-5.00	Very Serious (VS)
4	3.41-4.20	Serious (S)
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Serious (MS)
2	1.81-2.60	Slightly Serious (SS)
1	1.00-1.80	Least Serious (LS)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2. Respondents by Age

Particulars	School Heads		Teachers	
	F	%	F	%
21-25 years old	0	0	1	2.50
26-30 years old	0	0	5	12.50
31-35 years old	0	0	9	12.50
36-40 years old	2	8.33	5	22.50
41-45 years old	5	20.83	8	12.50
46-50 years old	6	25.00	3	20.00
51-55 years old	5	20.83	3	7.50
56 years old and above	6	25.00	4	7.50

Total	24	100.00	40	10.00
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Age stratification shows that 2 or 8.33 percent of the school heads are 36-40 years old, 5 or 20.83 percent each are 41-45 years old and 51-55 years old, and 6 or 25.00 percent each are 46-50 years old and 56 years old and above. The table further reveals that most of the school head respondents are 46-50 years old and 56 years old and above which is a good indication that they are more or less experienced as far as dealing with life is concerned and it may be an advantage in the field of management.

Meanwhile, out of 40 teachers-respondents, 1 or 2.50 percent is 21-25 years old, 5 or 12.50 percent each are 26-30 years old and 36-40 years old, 9 or 22.50 percent are 31-35 years old, 8 or 20.00 percent are 41-45 years old, 3 or 7.50 percent each are 46-50 years old and 51-55 years old, and 4 or 10.00 percent each are 56 years old and above. It can be gleaned further that most of the teacher-respondents are 31-35 years old. This indicates that they are mature enough to handle groups of learners as they are regarded as the front liners in the educative process of children.

Table 3. Respondents by Gender

Particulars	School Heads		Teachers	
	F	%	F	%
Male	6	25.00	1	2.50
Female	18	75.00	39	97.50
Total	24	100.00	40	100.00

The tables show that 6 or 25.00 percent of the school heads are male, while 18 or 75.00 percent of them are female. In the teacher's group, 1 or 2.50 percent is male, and 39 or 97.50 percent are female. This is an indication that there are more female respondents in both groups of respondents.

Table 4. Respondents by Civil Status

Particulars	School Heads		Teachers	
	F	%	F	%
Single	2	8.33	4	10.00
Married	21	87.50	34	85.00
Widowed	1	4.17	2	5.00

Total	24	100.00	40	100.00
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As a civil status, 2 or 8.33 percent of the school heads are single, 21 or 87.50 percent are married, and 1 or 2.50 percent are widowed. On the other hand, 4 or 10 percent of the teacher-respondents are single, 34 or 85.00 percent are married, and 2 or 5.00 percent are widowed. The table further reveals that there is dominance of married respondents in both groups. It is said that married people are more emotionally stable and more responsible for tasks accorded to them. Married persons are more mature when it comes to teaching and managing tasks. This can be attributed to their experiences in holding key roles in their families.

Table 5. Responded by Highest Educational Attainment

Particulars	School Heads		Teachers	
	F	%	F	%
Bachelor's Degree Graduate	0	0	2	5.00
MAEd Graduate	8	33.33	8	20.00
EdD/PhD Graduate	3	12.50	1	2.50
With MAEd Units	10	41.67	27	67.50
With EdD/PhD Units	3	12.67	2	5.00
Total	24	100.00	40	100.00

Relative to the highest educational attainment of school heads, 8 or 33.33 percent are MAEd graduates, 3 or 12.50 percent are EdD/PhD graduates, 10 or 41.67 percent have MAEd units, and 3 or 12.50 percent have EdD/PhD units. This implies that school heads have varying levels of educational attainment dominated by those who have MAEd units. The table also reflects that teachers claimed that 2 or 5.00 percent each are bachelor's degree graduates and have EdD/Phd units, 8 or 20.00 percent are MAEd graduates, 1 or 2.50 pursued EdD/PhD, and 27 or 67.50 percent have MAEd units. This implies that teachers have varying levels of educational attainment dominated by those who have MAEd units. These are indications that they have engaged themselves in enhancing their skills and capability by pursuing a master's degree or doctorate.

Table 6. Respondents by Present Position

Particulars	School Heads		Teachers	
	F	%	F	%
Principal 1	8	33.33	0	0
Principal 2	5	20.83	0	0
Principal 3	1	4.17	0	0
Head Teacher	6	25.00	0	0
Teacher 1	0	0	5	12.50
Teacher 3	0	0	32	80.00
Master Teacher 1	1	4.17	1	2.50
5Master Teacher 2	3	12.50	2	5.00
Total	24	100.00	40	10.00

It can be deduced from the table that 8 or 33.33 percent of the school heads are currently holding Principal 1 positions, positions 5 or 20.83 percent are Principal 2, 1 or 4.17 percent each is Principal 3, and Master Teacher 1, 6 or 25.00 percent are Head Teachers and 3 or 12.50 percent are Master Teachers 2. This suggests that the respondents of this study are currently holding different administrative positions, most of them are Principal 1.

As to teacher-respondents, 5 or 12.50 percent are teacherb1, 32 or 80.00 percent are Teacher 3, 1 or 2.50 percent are Master Teacher 1, and 2 or 5.00 percent are Master Teacher 2. This suggests that teacher-respondents of this study are currently holding different teaching positions, most of them are Teacher 3.

Table 7. Respondents as to the Latest Performance Rating

Particulars	School Heads		Teachers	
	F	%	F	%
Outstanding	24	100.00	36	90.00
Very Satisfactory	0	0	4	10.00
Satisfactory	0	0	0	0

Total	24	100.00	40	100.00
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The table shows that all of the 24 school heads are recipients of outstanding performance ratings. As to teachers, 36, or 90.00 percent received outstanding ratings, 4 or 10.00 percent are receipts of satisfactory merit, and none of them received very satisfactory ratings. These indicate that their performances are relatively good as far as their teaching and administrative careers are concerned.

Table 8. Respondents by Length of Service

Particulars	School Heads		Teachers	
	F	%	F	%
1-5 years	0	0	7	17.50
6-10 years	1	4.17	11	27.50
11-15 years	5	20.83	8	20.00
16-20 years old	4	16.67	6	15.00
21-25 years old	3	12.50	5	12.50
26-30 years old	8	33.33	0	0
31 years above	3	12.50	3	7.50
Total	24	100.00	40	100.00

It can be gleaned from the table that 1 or 4.17 percent of the school heads have been in service for 6-10 years, 5 or 20.83 percent for 11-15 years, 4 or 16.67 percent for 16-20 years, 3 or 12.50 percent each for 21-25 years and 31 years and above, and 8 or 33.33 percent for 26-30 years. On the other hand, 7 or 17.50 of teachers claimed they had been in the teaching profession for 1-5 years, 11 or 27.50 percent were in service for 6-10 years, 8 or 20.00 percent for 11-15 years, 6 or 15.00 percent for 16-20 years, 5 or 12.50 percent for 21-25 years, and 3 or 7.50 percent for at least 31 years. It can be noted that the school heads and teachers have varying lengths of years in service which is attributed to the differences in their management and teaching experiences.

Table 9. Respondents by Level of In-Service Training Attended

Particulars	School Heads	Teachers
International Level	18	11
National Level	21	20
Regional Level	24	23
Division Level	24	32
District Level	24	40
School Level	24	40

It is evident from the table that all the school head- respondents have attended in-service trainings at the school, district, division, and regional levels, 21 at the national levels, and 18 of them claimed that they have been in the international level in-service trainings. The table further shows all of the teacher-respondents have attended the in-service training at the school and district levels, 32 at the division level, 23 at the regional level, 20 at the national level, and 11 at the international level. This suggests that school heads and teachers are keeping themselves abreast with the trends in teaching and school management by attending seminars and trainings at various levels.

Table 10. Extent of Use of the Different Methods in Reading Instruction

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M.	Q.D.	Rank	W.M.	Q.D.	Rank
1. Phonics Method	4.71	VO	1	4.68	VO	1
2. The look and say Method	4.33	VO	2	4.45	VO	2
3. The Language Experience Approach	4.08	O	3	4.15	O	3
4. The Context Support Method	3.96	O	4	4.08	O	4
Average Weighted Mean	4.27	Very Often		4.34	Very Often	

The table shows the extent of use of the different methods in reading instruction where “Phonics Method” and “The look and say Method” are “very often” used with weighted means of 4.71 and 4.33, respectively; while “The Language Experience Approach” and “The Context Support Method” are “often” utilized with weighted means of 4.08 and 3.96, respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.27 implies that the different

methods are “very often” used in reading instruction as affirmed by school head-respondents.

Meanwhile, teacher-respondents affirmed that “Phonics Method” and “The Look and say Method” is ‘very often’ utilized with weighted means of 4.68 and 4.45, respectively; while “The Language Experience Approach” and “The Context Support Method” are ‘often’ employed with weighted means of 4.15 and 4.08, respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.34 demonstrates that the different methods are “very often” used in reading instruction as perceived by teacher-respondents.

Table 11. Extent of Use of the Different Strategies in Reading Instruction

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M.	Q.D.	Rank	W.M.	Q.D.	Rank
1. Focus on Fluency and Phonics Simultaneously	4.67	VO	1	4.65	VO	2
2. Explicitly Teach and Display Strategies	4.58	VO	2	4.70	VO	1
3. Graphic Organizers	4.33	VO	5	4.28	VO	8.5
4. Employ the 3-2-1 Strategy	4.04	O	10.5	4.20	O	11
5. Decoding: Focus on Problem Sounds	4.13	O	8.5	4.23	VO	10
6. Use Metacognition	4.13	O	8.5	4.28	VO	8.5
7. Make It Personal	4.00	O	12	4.15	O	12.5
8. Word Walls	3.83	O	14.5	4.05	O	14
9. More than Just Books	3.88	O	13	4.15	O	12.5
10. Voice and Choice	4.04	O	10.5	4.43	VO	7
11. Integrate Technology	4.50	VO	3	4.63	VO	3
12. Write to Read	4.25	VO	6.5	4.53	VO	5
13. Make it A Game	4.25	VO	6.5	4.48	VO	6
14. Avoid Over-Correcting	3.83	O	14.5	4.00	O	15
15. Offer Proper Praise	4.38	VO	4	4.60	VO	4

Average Weighted Mean	4.19	Very Often	4.36	Very Often
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Relative to the extent of use of strategies, the following are “very often” used in reading instruction as claimed by school heads; “Focus on Fluency and Phonics Simultaneously” with a weighted mean of 4.67, “Explicitly Teach and Display Strategies” with a weighted mean of 4.58, “Integrate Technology” at 4.50 “Other Proper Praise” at 4.38, “Graphic Organizers” at 4.33, as well as “Write to Read” and “Make it a Game” sharing a weighted mean of 4.25, while the following strategies are “often” used; “Decoding: Focus on Problem Sounds” and “Use Metacognition” with a common weighted mean of 4.13, ‘Employ the 3-2-1 Strategy and “Voice and Choice” sharing a weighted mean of 4.04, “Make it Personal” at 4.00, “More Than Just Books” at 3.68, as well as “Word Walls” and “Avoid Over-Correcting” with a common weighted mean of 3.83. The Average weighted mean of 4.19 denotes that school heads perceived the different strategies to be “often” used in reading instruction.

On the other hand, teacher-respondents affirmed that the following strategies are “very often” utilized in reading instruction: “Explicitly Teach and Display Strategies” with a weighted mean of 4.70, “Focus on Fluency and Phonics Simultaneously” with a weighted mean of 4.65, ‘Integrate Technology’ at 4.63, ‘Offer Proper Praise’ at 4.60, ‘Write to Read’ at 4.53, ‘Make It A Game’ at 4.48, ‘Voice and Choice’ at 4.43, ‘Graphic Organizers’ and ‘Use Metacognition’ sharing a weighted mean of 4.28, as well as ‘Decoding: Focus on Problem Sounds’ at 4.23, while the following strategies are ‘often’ used: ‘Employ the 3-2-1 strategy’ with a weighted mean of 4.20, ‘Make It Personal’ and ‘More Than Just Books’ sharing a weighted mean of 4.15, as well as ‘Word Walls’ and ‘Avoid Over-Correcting’ with weighted means of 4.05 and 4.00, respectively. The Average weighted mean of 4.36 is the teacher’s affirmation that the different strategies are “very often” used in reading instruction.

Table 12. Extent of Use of the Different Approaches in Reading Instruction

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M	Q.D	Rank	W.M	Q.D	Rank
1. Phonics or bottom-up Approach	4.54	VO	1	4.50	VO	1
2. Whole Word or Top Down Approach	4.04	O	5	4.23	VO	5
3. Basal Reader Approach or Whole Language Approach	4.04	O	5	4.13	O	7
4. Literature-Based Approach	3.58	O	7	4.20	O	6
5. Language Experience Approach	4.04	O	5	4.25	VO	4
6. Interactive Model	4.13	O	2	4.48	VO	2

7. Balanced Approach	4.08	O	3	4.30	O	3
Average Weighted Mean	4.06	Often		4.30	Very Often	

It can be gleaned from the table that “Phonics or Bottom-up Approach” is a “very often” used approach in reading instruction as claimed by school head- respondents with a weighted mean of 4.54, while the following approaches are “often “: used “ Interactive Model “ with a weighted mean of 4.13, “ Balanced Approach” at 4.08 “Whole Word Top, “ Basal Reader Approach or Whole Language Approach”, and “Language Experience sharing a weighted mean of 4.04, as well as “ Literature-Based Approach” at 3.58. The average weighted mean of 4.08 suggests that the different approaches are “often” used in reading instruction as claimed by school-head respondents.

Meanwhile, teachers affirmed that the following approaches are “very often “ utilized: “Phonics or Bottom-up Approach “ with a weighted mean of 4.50, “Interactive Model” at 4.48 “Balanced Approach” at 4.30, as well as “Language Experience Approach “ and “Whole Word Top Down Approach” with a weighted mean of 4.25 and 4.23, respectively while “ Literature Based Approach” and “Basal Reader Approach or Whole Language Approach” are “often” used with weighted means of 4.20 and 4.13 respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.30 is an indication that the different approaches are “very often” used in reading instruction as affirmed by teacher-respondents.

Table 13. Extent of Effect of the Different Methods in Reading Instruction

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M	Q.D	Rank	W.M	Q.D	Rank
1 Phonics Method	4.75	VE	1	4.68	VE	1
2.The look and say Method	4.54	VE	2	4.58	VE	2
3.The Language Experience Approach	4.46	VE	3	4.43	VE	3
4.The Context Support Method	4.33	VE	4	4.35	VE	4
Average Weighted Mean	4.52		Very Effective	4.51		Very Effective

In terms of the effect of the different methods in reading instruction, school heads affirmed that the following methods are “very effective”: “Phonics Method” with a weighted mean of 4.75, “ The Look and Say Method” at 4.54, and “ The Language Experience Approach” and “The context Support Method” with weighted means of 4.46 and 4.33, respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.52 suggests that the different methods are “very effective” in reading instruction as perceived by school heads.

Meanwhile, teacher-respondents claimed that the following methods are “very effective” in reading instruction. “Phonics Method” with a weighted mean of 4.68 as well as “The Look and Say Method”, “The Language Experience Approach” and “The Context Support Method” with weighted means of 4.58, 4.43, and 4.35, respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.51 denoted that teacher-respondents believed that the different methods are “very effective” in reading instruction.

Table 14. Extent of Effect of the Different Strategies in Reading Instruction

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M.	Q.D.	Rank	W.M.	Q.D.	Rank
1. Focus on Fluency and Phonics Simultaneously	4.50	VE	3	4.63	VE	1
2. Explicitly Teach and Display Strategies	4.79	VE	1	4.60	VE	2
3. Graphic Organizers	4.38	VE	6	4.45	VE	6.5
4. Employ the 3-2-1 Strategy	4.13	VE	13	4.10	E	15
5. Decoding: Focus on Problem Sounds	4.29	VE	10.5	4.33	VE	8
6. Use Metacognition	4.29	VE	10.5	4.27	VE	10
7. Make It Personal	4.17	VE	12	4.15	E	12.5
8. Words Walls	4.33	VE	8.5	4.15	E	12.5
9. More Than Just Books	4.08	VE	14	4.18	E	11
10. Voice and Choice	4.33	VE	8.5	4.30	VE	9
11. Integrate Technology	4.54	VE	2	4.50	VE	4.5
12. Write to Read	4.46	VE	4	4.45	VE	6.5
13. Make It A Game	4.38	VE	6	4.53	VE	3
14. Avoid Over-Correcting	3.98	VE	15	4.13	E	14
15. Offer Proper Praise	4.38	VE	6	4.50	VE	4.5

Average Weighted Mean	4.34	Very Effective	4.35	Very Effective
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With regards to the extent of the effect of the different strategies in reading instruction, school heads claimed that the following strategies are “very effective” “Explicitly Teach and Display Strategies” with a weighted mean of 4.79,

“Integrate Technology” with a weighted mean of 4.54, “Focus on Fluency and Phonics Simultaneously” at 4.50, “Write to Read at 4.46, “Graphic Organizers”, “Make It A Game”, and “ Offer Proper Praise” with a common weighted mean of 4.38, “Word Walls” and “Voice and Choice” sharing a weighted mean of 4.33, as well as “Decoding: Focus on Problem Sounds “ and “ Use Metacognition “ which both registered a weighted mean of 4.29; while the following strategies are “effective” “Make It Personal “ with a weighted mean of 4.17, as well as “Employ the 3-2-1 Strategy”, “More Than Just Books”, and “Avoid Over-Correcting” with weighted means of 4.13, 4.08 and 3.98, respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.34 indicates that the different methods are “very effective” in reading instruction as perceived by school heads.

On the other hand, teacher-respondents perceived the following strategies as “very effective” in reading instruction: “Focus on Fluency and Phonics Simultaneously” with a weighted mean of 4.63, “Explicitly Teach and Display Strategies” with a weighted mean of 4.60, “Make It A Game” at 4.53, “Integrate Technology” and “Offer Proper Praise sharing a weighted mean of 4.50, “Graphic Organizers” and “Write to Read” with a common weighted mean of 4.45, as well as “Decoding: Focus on Problem Sounds”, “Voice and Choice”, and “Use Metacognition” with weighted means of 4.33, 4.30 and 4.27 respectively, while the following strategies are “effective”. “ More Than Just Books” at 4.18 , “Make It Personal “ and “ Word Walls” with a common weighted mean of 4.15, as well as “Avoid Over-Correcting” and “Employ the 3-2-1 Strategy” with weighted means of 4.13 and 4.10, respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.35 suggests that teacher-respondents believed that the different strategies are “very effective” in reading instruction.

Table 15. Extent of Effect of the Different Approaches in Reading Instruction

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M	Q.D.	Rank	W.M	Q.D.	Rank
1. Phonics or bottom-up Approach	4.58	VE	1	4.45	VE	2
2. Whole Word or Top Down Approach	4.38	VE	2	4.35	VE	5
3. Basal Reader Approach or Whole Language Approach	4.13	E	6	4.35	VE	5
4. Literature-Based Approach	3.96	E	7	4.18	E	7
5. Language Experience Approach	4.23	VE	4.5	4.35	VE	5

6. Interactive Model	4.33	VE	3	4.50	VE	1
7. Balanced Approach	4.23	VE	4.5	4.40	VE	3
Average Weighted Mean	4.23	Very Effective		4.37	Very Effective	

In relation to the different approaches, school heads claimed that the following are "very effective" in reading instruction: "Phonics or Bottom-up Approach " with a weighted mean of 4.58, " Whole Word or Top-Down Approach " at 4.38, "Interactive Model" at 4.33, as well as "Language Experience Approach" and "Balanced Approach or Whole Language Approach" and "Literature -Based Approach" are "effective" with weighted means of 4.13 and 3.96, respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.23 denotes that the different approaches are "very effective" in reading instruction as affirmed by school head respondents. On the part of teachers, the following approaches are "very effective": " Interactive Model" with a weighted mean of 4.50, "Phonics or Bottom-Up Approach "at 4.45 "Balanced Approach" at 4.40, as well as "Whole Word or Top-Down Approach", "Basal Reader Approach", and "Language Experience Approach" which all registered a weighted mean of 4.35, whole "Literature-Based Approach" id "effective" with a weighted mean of 4.18. The average weighted mean of 4.37 implies that the different approaches are "very effective" in reading instruction as claimed by teacher-respondents.

Table 16. Extent of Pupil’s Manifestation of Reading Difficulties

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M	Q.D.	Rank	W.M	Q.D.	Rank
1. Omission (omits a letter, word, or sentence while reading)	4.33	VO	4.5	4.30	VO	3
2. Addition (adds letters or words)	4.21	VO	6	4.15	O	6
3. Substitution (substitutes a word/ letter for another)	4.33	VO	4.5	4.20	O	4.5
4. Mispronunciation of words	4.46	VO	1	4.35	VO	2
5. Stress and intonation	4.38	VO	3	4.20	O	4.5
6. Phrasing	4.42	VO	2	4.50	VO	1

Average Weighted Mean	4.36	Very Often	4.28	Very Often
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Assessing the extent of pupils' manifestation of reading difficulties reveals that the following difficulties are "very often" manifested as perceived by school heads: "Mispronunciation of words" with a weighted mean of 4.46, "Phrasing with a weighted mean of 4.42, " Stress and intonation" at 4.38, "Omission (omits a letter, word or sentence while reading)" and "Substitution (substitutes a word/ letter for another)" with a common weighted mean of 4.33, as well as "Addition (adds letters or words)" at 4.21. The average weighted mean of 4.36 implies that pupils "very often" manifest reading difficulties as claimed by school head- respondents. Meanwhile, teacher-respondents affirmed that pupils "very often" manifest the following reading difficulties: "Phrasing " with a weighted mean of 4.50, "Mispronunciation of words" with a weighted mean of 4.35, and "Omission (omits a letter, word or sentence while reading)" at 4.30, whole pupils "often" manifest the following reading difficulties: "Substitution (substitutes a word/letter for another)" and "Stress and intonation" sharing a weighted mean of 4.20 as well as "Addition (adds letters or words)" with a weighted mean of 4.15. The average weighted mean of 4.28 indicates that pupils "very often" manifest reading difficulties as teacher-respondents perceive.

Table 17. Extent of Manifestation of the Different Causes of Pupil's Reading Difficulties

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M	Q.D.	Rank	W.M	Q.D.	Rank
1. Child cannot communicate in English	4.46	VO	1	4.50	VO	1
2. Mother tongue interference	44.04	O	2	4.33	VO	3
3. Lack of motivation	3.63	O	8	3.85	O	7.5
4. Laziness	3.88	O	4	4.48	VO	2
5. Chronic Diseases	3.33	So	11.5	3.30	So	12
6. Lack of textbooks and reading materials	3.63	O	8	3.75	O	10
7. Past continuous failure in schoolwork	3.42	O	10	3.63	O	11
8. Lack of support by parents	3.96	O	3	3.90	O	6
9. Effects of poverty	3.63	O	8	3.80	O	9
10. Genetic problems	3.33	So	11.5	3.85	O	7.5
11. Parents illiteracy level	3.75	O	5.5	4.25	VO	4

12. Overloading of curriculum	3.75	O	5.5	3.93	O	5
13. Poor Teaching	3.29	So	13	3.23	So	13
14. Poor learning environment	3.04	So	14	3.13	So	14
Average Weighted Mean	3.65	Often	often	3.85	Often	

Consonant to the causes of reading difficulties, school head-respondents affirmed that "Child cannot communicate in English" is "very often" the cause of reading difficulty with a weighted mean of 4.46, while the following are "often" cause reading difficulty among pupils: "Mother tongue interference" with weighted mean of 4.04, "Lack of support by parents" at 3.96, "Laziness" at 3.88, "Parents illiteracy level" and "Overloading of curriculum" with a common weighted mean of 3.75, "Lack of motivation", "Lack of textbooks and reading materials", and "Effects of poverty" with a common weighted mean of 3.63, as well as "Past continuous failure in schoolwork" at 3.42. Meanwhile, the following "sometimes" cause reading difficulty among pupils: "Chronic diseases" and "Genetic problems" sharing a weighted mean of 3.33 as well as "Poor teaching" and "Poor learning environment" with weighted mean of 3.29 and 3.04, respectively. The average weighted mean of 3.65 suggests that reading difficulties among pupils are "often" caused by different factors as claimed by school heads. Meanwhile, teacher-respondents perceived that the following are the "very often" causes of reading difficulty among pupils: "Child cannot communicate in English" with a weighted mean of 4.50 "Laziness" with a weighted mean of 4.48 "Mother tongue interference" at 4.33 as well as "Parents illiteracy level" at 4.25 while the following "often" cause pupils' reading difficulties: "Overloading of curriculum" with a weighted mean of 3.93, "Lack of support by parents" at 3.90, "Lack of motivation" and "Genetics problems" sharing a weighted mean of 3.85 as well as "Effects of poverty", "Lack of textbooks and reading materials" and "Past continuous failure in schoolwork" with weighted mean of 3.80, 3.75 and 3.63 respectively. On the other hand, the following "sometimes" cause reading difficulties: "Chronic diseases", "Poor teaching", and "Poor learning environment" with weighted mean of 3.30, 3.23 and 3.13, respectively. The average weighted mean of 3.85 denotes that reading difficulties among pupils are "often" caused by various factors as affirmed by teacher-respondents.

Table 18. Extent of Use of the Different Measures to Address Pupil's Reading Difficulties

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M	Q.D.	Rank	W.M	Q.D.	Rank
1. Remedial Work	4.71	VO	1	4.70	VO	1
2. Reading circle	4.33	VO	2	4.38	VO	2
3. Extensive reading	4.54	VO	3	4.48	VO	3

4. Including more reading activities in the lesson	4.67	VO	4	4.55	VO	4
Average Weighted Mean	4.56	Very Often		4.53	Very Often	

The table reflects that the following measures are "very often" used to address pupils' reading difficulties as claimed by school heads: "Remedial work" with a weighted mean of 4.71, "Including more reading activities in the lesson" with a weighted mean of 4.67, as well as "Extensive reading" and "Reading circle" with weighted means of 4.54 and 4.33 respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.56 indicates that the different measures are "very often" used to address pupils' reading difficulties as claimed by school head- respondents. Meanwhile, teacher-respondents affirmed that the following measures are "very often" utilized to address the reading difficulties of pupils: "Remedial work" with a weighted mean of 4.70, as well as "Including more reading activities in the lesson", "Extensive reading" and "Reading circle" with weighted means of 4.55, 4.48, and 4.38, respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.53 suggests that the different measures are "very often" used for pupils' reading difficulties as claimed by teacher-respondents.

Table 19. Extent of Effects of the Different Measures to Address Pupils' Reading Difficulties

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M	Q.D.	Rank	W.M	Q.D.	Rank
1. Remedial Work	4.67	VE	1	4.78	VE	1
2. Reading circle	4.54	VE	2	4.58	VE	2
3. Extensive reading	4.63	VE	2.5	4.68	VE	3
4. Including more reading activities in the lesson	4.63	VE	2.5	4.50	VE	4
Average Weighted Mean	4.62	Very Effective		4.64	Very Effective	

Relative to the effect of the different measures to address pupils reading difficulties, school heads believed that the following measures are "very effective" "Remedial work" with a weighted mean of 4.67, "Extensive reading" and " Including more reading activities in the lesson" sharing a weighted mean of 4.63, as well as "Reading circle" at 4.54. The average weighted mean of 4.62 denotes that the different measures are "very effective " in addressing pupils' reading difficulties as affirmed by school head - respondents. On the other hand, teachers perceived the following measures as "very effective" in addressing pupils' reading difficulties: "Remedial work" with a weighted mean of 4.78 as well as "Extensive reading", "Reading circle", and "Including more reading

activities in the lesson" with a weighted mean of 4.68, 4.58, and 4.50, respectively. The average weighted mean of 4.64 implies that the different measures are "very effective" in addressing pupils' reading difficulties as claimed by teacher-respondents.

Table 20. Extent of the Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Reading Instruction

PARTICULARS	School Heads			Teachers		
	W.M	Q.D.	Rank	W.M	Q.D.	Rank
1. Lack of effective teaching material	3.54	S	5	3.30	MS	1
2. Large number of pupils in a class	3.63	S	4	3.65	S	2
3. Pupils' poor background knowledge	3.50	S	6	4.08	S	6.5
4. Teaching pronunciation	3.13	MS	8	3.23	MS	15
5. Lack of support by parents	3.75	S	3	3.88	S	8
6. Work overload	3.92	S	2	3.80	S	10
7. Poor learning environment	3.21	MS	7	3.33	MS	12.5
8. Lack of administrative supervisory support	3.08	MS	9	2.88	MS	12.5
9. Lack of support from co-teachers	2.54	SS	10	2.78	MS	11
10. Lack of pupils' interest	4.17	S	1	4.08	S	9
Average Weighted Mean	3.45	Serious		3.50	Serious	

Taking into consideration the challenges encountered by teachers in reading instruction, school heads claimed that the following challenges are "serious" "Lack of pupils' interest" with a weighted mean of 4.17, "Work overload" with a weighted mean of 3.92 "Lack of support by parents" at 3.75 as well as "A large number of pupils in a class", "Lack of effective teaching material". "Pupils poor background knowledge" with weighted means of 3.63, 3.54, and 3.50, respectively: while the following challenges are "moderately serious", "Poor learning environment", "Teaching pronunciation", and "Lack of administrative and supervisory support " with a weighted mean of 3.21, 3.13 and 3.08, respectively Meanwhile, "Lack of support from co-teachers" isa "slightly serious" with a weighted mean of 2.54. The average weighted mean of 3.45 indicates that there is the seriousness of the challenges encountered by teachers in reading instruction as affirmed

by school heads. On the other hand, teacher-respondents claimed that the following challenges are "serious". "Pupils poor background knowledge " and "Lack of pupils' interest" with a common weighted mean of 4.08, as well as "Lack of support by parents", "Work overload", and "Large numbers of pupils in a class" with weighted means of 3.88, 3.80 and 3.65, respectively. At the same time, the following challenges are "moderately serious": "Poor learning environment" with a weighted mean of 3.33, "Lack of effective teaching material" at 3.30, as well as "Teaching pronunciation", "Lack of administrative and supervisory support", and "Lack of support from co-teachers" with a weighted mean of 3.23, 2.88 and 2.78, respectively. The average weighted means of 3.50 implies that there is seriousness of the challenges encountered by teachers in reading instruction as claimed by teacher-respondents

Table 21. T-test Result of the Perceptions of School Heads and Teachers Regarding the Reading Difficulties of Learners and the Challenges Faced by Teachers in Reading Instruction In Public Elementary Schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela

PARTICULARS	t- computed	P-value	Result	Decision
1. Extent of Manifestation of Pupils' Reading Difficulties	1. 12621	.143189	S	Reject Ho
2. Extent of the Challenges Encountered by Teacher in Reading Instruction	-0.25706	.400023	NS	Accept Ho

It is evident from the table that the p-values on the following: "Extent of Manifestation of Pupils' Reading Difficulties" and "Extent of the Challenges Encountered by Teacher in Reading Instruction" are higher than .05, hence the null hypothesis that "there is no significant difference exists between the perceptions of schools heads and teachers concerning the reading difficulties of Grade 1 learners and the challenges faced by teachers in teaching reading in public elementary schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela: is rejected.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are made:

Most of the school head-respondents are married females who are 46-50 years old and 56 years old and above, with MAEd units, holding Principal 1 positions, recipients of outstanding performance ratings, in service for 26-30 years, and have attended in-service training in the regional level. On the other hand, most of the teachers are married females who are 31-35 years old, with MAEd units, holding Teacher 3 positions, recipients of outstanding ratings, in service for 6-10 years, and have attended district in-service trainings.

The different methods, strategies, and approaches are very often used to effectively teach reading among Grade 1 pupils. Meanwhile, pupils very often manifest reading difficulties often caused by various factors. Furthermore, teachers very often used different measures to effectively address pupils' reading difficulties. Moreover, there is seriousness of the challenges encountered by teachers in reading instruction.

Finally, there is no significant difference exists between the perceptions of school heads and teachers with regard to the reading difficulties of Grade 1 learners and the challenges faced by teachers reading in public elementary schools in Legislative District 3, Isabela.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended for implementation:

1. Since it was found that the different methods, strategies, and approaches are very effective in reading instruction, these must be continuously utilized to further enhance learners' reading skills.
2. Since the different measures are very effective in addressing the reading difficulties of pupils, there is a need to sustain their use to promote the reading skills and abilities of the learners.
3. Since the challenges encountered by teachers in reading instruction are serious, there is a need to address these challenges in order to maximize the teaching-learning experiences in the classrooms, especially in reading.
4. School heads and teachers should continue attending trainings for capacity development on the aspects of reading instruction for the promotion of more effective and varied teaching-learning experiences.
5. This study was limited to the teachers in elementary schools in Legislative Districts 3: Therefore, the sample for the study should be increased to involve elementary schools in the School Division of Isabela. Both public and private, in order to get richer data from different contexts.
6. Future researchers who would like to study topics related to the research study undertaken could investigate the extent of reading's effect on learners' academic performance.
7. Further Study along this line is likewise recommended.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirms compliance with ethical research standards, ensuring informed consent, anonymity, and respondents' well-being, safeguarding their freedom to withdraw, avoiding plagiarism and bias, and using findings solely for academic purposes without conflicts of interest.

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